

exercice DM course

Law & Criminology DMP

Admin details

Project Name exercice DM course

Project Identifier abcd

Grant Title efgh

Principal Investigator / Researcher Karoline Helldorff

Description administrative and constitutional law in public sector
accounting standardisation

Institution Ghent University

Administrative Data

Date of first version

Question not answered.

Date of last update

Question not answered.

1. Data Collection

1.1 What data will you collect or create?

textual digital data in text documents and spreadsheets;
processed data derived from laws and literature

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1.2 How will the data be collected or created?

no standards or methodologies apply;
structure: yymmddtopic
unfortunately no strategy for version control yet

quality assurance is a good question

2. Data Documentation and Metadata

2.1 How will you document the data?

Question not answered.

3. Ethics, Legal Issues and Confidentiality

3.1 How will you manage ethics? Choose one of the options from the dropdown menu and briefly motivate your choice in the 'Comment' box below.

Question not answered.

3.2 How will you manage any confidentiality issues?

Question not answered.

3.3 How will you manage intellectual property rights issues?

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Question not answered.

4. Data Storage and Backup during Research

4.1 How will you store and backup data during research?

Question not answered.

4.2 How will you ensure that stored data are secure?

Question not answered.

5. Data Selection and Preservation after Research

5.1 Which data should be retained for preservation and/or sharing?

Question not answered.

5.2 What is the long-term preservation plan for the selected datasets?

Question not answered.

6. Data Sharing

6.1 Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

Question not answered.

6.2 How will you share data selected for sharing?

Question not answered.

7. Responsibilities and Resources

7.1 Who will be responsible for data management?

Question not answered.

7.2 Will you need additional resources to implement your DMP?

Question not answered.